

**MINISTRY OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING
FPT UNIVERSITY**

Evaluating Methods For Applying Large Concept Model To Image
Captioning

by

Huynh Minh Triet

A thesis submitted in conformity with the requirements
for the degree of Master of Software Engineering

© Copyright by Huynh Minh Triet 2025

**MINISTRY OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING
FPT UNIVERSITY**

Evaluating Methods For Applying Large Concept Model To Image
Captioning

by

Huynh Minh Triet

A thesis submitted in conformity with the requirements
for the degree of Master of Software Engineering

Supervisor:

1. Doan Xuan Huy Minh

© Copyright by Huynh Minh Triet 2025

Evaluating Methods For Applying Large Concept Model To Image Captioning

Huynh Minh Triet

Degree Master of Software Engineering

FPT University

2025

Abstract

This thesis investigates the application of Large Concept Models (LCMs) to image captioning, a task requiring both visual recognition and linguistic reasoning. Unlike Transformer-based captioners that optimize token likelihood, LCMs internalize high-dimensional concept representations, enabling richer semantic abstraction. We integrate LCMs into a prefix-based captioning framework and introduce Prefix Concept Extraction (PCE), which converts image embeddings into pseudo-tokens for explicit cross-modal alignment. Experiments on Flickr30k demonstrate that LCM-based captioners consistently outperform GPT-2 baselines under frozen language model training, achieving higher BLEU, METEOR, ROUGE, CIDEr, and BERTScore metrics. While GPT-2 remains competitive when fine-tuned, LCM variants show stronger semantic fidelity and generalization. Finally, we implement the proposed models as an extension for Stable Diffusion WebUI, enabling practical deployment for dataset creation and real-world usage. These findings highlight concept-based modeling as a promising alternative to sequence likelihood optimization in multimodal learning.

Keywords: Image Captioning, Large Concept Models, Multimodal, CLIP, GPT-2, Cocomix, Flickr30k

Acknowledgments

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my supervisor, Doan Xuan Huy Minh, for his invaluable guidance, encouragement, and constructive feedback throughout the course of this research. I am also grateful to the faculty members of FPT University for providing the academic environment and resources that made this work possible. Finally, I extend heartfelt appreciation to my family for their unwavering patience, understanding, and encouragement during my studies.

Table of Contents

Contents

Abstract.....	1
Acknowledgments	2
Table of Contents	3
List of Tables	5
List of Figures.....	6
List of Abbreviations	7
Chapter 1 INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1. Background.....	1
1.2. Problem Statement.....	2
1.3. Research Objectives.....	2
1.4. Research Scope	3
Chapter 2 LITERATURE REVIEW	4
2.1. Vision-Language Modeling	4
2.2. Transformer Alternatives	4
2.3. Large Concept Models.....	5
Chapter 3 METHODOLOGIES	7
3.1. ClipCap	7

3.2.	Continuous Concept Mixing	8
3.3.	Our proposal	9
3.4.	Prefix Concept Extraction.....	11
Chapter 4	IMPLEMENTATION	12
4.1.	Dataset Overview.....	12
4.2.	Dataset Preparation	12
4.3.	Training and Evaluation Configuration	12
4.4.	Stable Diffusion WebUI and Extension.....	13
Chapter 5	RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.....	15
5.1.	Results.....	15
5.2.	Discussion	16
Chapter 6	CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK.....	19
6.1.	Conclusion	19
6.2.	Future Work.....	20
References	21

List of Tables

Table 1. LLM architectures comparison.....	6
Table 2. Evaluation results	15
Table 3. Performance evaluation on Google Colab T4 GPU (frozen language model configuration)	16

List of Figures

Figure 1. ClipCap architecture	7
Figure 2. Cocomix architecture	8
Figure 3. ClipCap with Cocomix integration	10
Figure 4. Extension interface.....	13
Figure 5. Extension flow-chart	14
Figure 6. Evaluation comparison of models on BLEU-1, METEOR and BERTScore.....	16

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
BLEU	Bilingual Evaluation Understudy
CIDEr	Consensus-based Image Description Evaluation
CLIP	Contrastive Language-Image Pretraining
Cocomix	Continuous Concept Mixing
GPT	Generative Pretrained Transformer
LCM	Large Concept Model
METEOR	Metric for Evaluation of Translation with Explicit Ordering
PCE	Prefix Concept Extraction
ROUGE	Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation
SAE	Sparse Autoencoder

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Image captioning represents a key benchmark in multimodal learning, requiring the synthesis of visual perception and linguistic reasoning. The task demands not only the ability to recognize objects and actions but also to form coherent, contextually relevant descriptions that reflect conceptual understanding. Over the past few years, architectures based on Transformers [1] have become the dominant backbone for caption generation, primarily due to their strong sequence modeling capabilities and scalability across large datasets.

Despite their success, Transformers are inherently constrained by their design. As token-level pattern predictors, they optimize for next-token likelihood rather than semantic fidelity or conceptual grounding, lacking in true introspective or reasoning capabilities without verbal augmentation [2]. This results in outputs that are often fluent yet semantically shallow, capturing linguistic regularities rather than genuine understanding of the visual content. Moreover, the quadratic complexity of self-attention can limit efficiency when modeling long context windows or multimodal dependencies.

These challenges have catalyzed an active search for architectures that move beyond traditional attention mechanisms. Recent efforts have shown a growing shift in the field to develop architectures capable of deeper semantic abstraction, improved efficiency, and more robust cross-modal generalization. Within this context, Large Concept Models (LCMs) [3], [4] have emerged as a promising direction. Unlike language models that rely on statistical token prediction, LCMs internalize high-dimensional concept representations, allowing them to model relational and abstract semantics more naturally. However, due to the novelty of LCMs their potential for multimodal alignment tasks such as image captioning remains unexplored.

Beyond theoretical advances, the motivation for this study is driven by the increasing demand for image captioning systems in real-world applications such as accessibility tools for visually impaired users, automated content moderation, and dataset generation for

creative AI platforms. A system that can generate semantically rich and conceptually grounded captions would significantly improve user trust and broaden the scope of practical deployment. By exploring LCMs within this domain, this research aims to bridge the gap between academic innovation and practical utility, ensuring that multimodal AI systems can better serve both everyday users and specialized professional needs.

1.2. Problem Statement

While recent advances in multimodal learning have introduced powerful architectures to address the shortcoming of Transformers, there remains no systematic evaluation of LCMs for image captioning. The absence of methods that explicitly align visual embeddings with concept-level representations creates a gap in both theory and practice. This thesis addresses the problem of designing and assessing an LCM-based captioning framework that can achieve stronger semantic fidelity and cross-modal alignment than traditional Transformer-based approaches, while remaining practical.

1.3. Research Objectives

The primary objective of this research is to evaluate the efficacy of LCMs in the task of image captioning, comparing their performance to traditional Transformer-based captioning models. The study also aims to deploy the resulting captioning models as a public extension for the Stable Diffusion WebUI to enable real-world usage.

Research Question:

1. To what extent can LCM-based captioning systems outperform traditional Transformer-based image captioning methods when both are evaluated under comparable training constraints, architectural capacities, and multimodal alignment settings?
2. How does the incorporation of Prefix Concept Extraction (PCE) influence the quality of cross-modal alignment between visual embeddings and language representations within an LCM-based captioning framework, and what specific improvements does it provide compared to standard LCM training without PCE?

3. How can an LCM-based image captioning system be effectively implemented and integrated into real-world applications, particularly within the Stable Diffusion WebUI ecosystem, to enable practical deployment and user accessibility?

1.4. Research Scope

This thesis focuses on the evaluation and practical deployment of Large Concept Models (LCMs) for image captioning. The scope includes a direct comparison between LCM-based and Transformer-based approaches, with a particular emphasis on assessing semantic fidelity. The study also investigates the integration of Prefix Concept Extraction (PCE) into LCMs to enhance alignment between visual and language representations. Furthermore, the research encompasses the real-world implementation of the proposed LCM-based captioning system, specifically targeting its deployment as an extension for the Stable Diffusion WebUI. The thesis is limited to evaluating these models under comparable training conditions and architectural capacities, aiming to provide insights that are both academically rigorous and relevant for advancing accessible and effective image captioning solutions.

Chapter 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Vision-Language Modeling

The use of prefix-based models for image captioning, such as those that map image encoders to language models [5], [6], [7], has been widely adopted due to its simplicity and effectiveness. However, recent work in vision-language modelling has explored more diverse architectures that treat the visual and linguistic modalities with greater flexibility and scale.

One major trend is the design of large, generalist multimodal models that unify many vision-language tasks in a single end-to-end framework [8], [9], [10], [11]. This shift emphasizes joint modelling of perception, reasoning and generation rather than modular prefix mapping. Another direction emphasizes efficiency and scaling through sparse architectures and expert routing in multimodal models [12], [13]. These models represent a departure from dense Transformer decoders, illustrating how efficient architectures are becoming central to modern vision-language modelling.

2.2. Transformer Alternatives

Recent work exploring alternatives to the Transformer architecture has produced several promising directions that aim to improve efficiency, long-range modeling, or representational properties. A subset of these alternatives has already been adapted for vision-oriented tasks.

Mamba [14] is a family of structured state-space models that can achieve linear-time complexity. Its performance makes it a candidate backbone for vision implementation such as MambaVision [15], which combines Mamba blocks and Transformer layers to capture long-range spatial dependencies. RWKV [16] proposes a different tradeoff, it implements an RNN-style recurrence that is trained like a parallelizable transformer, yielding linear time and constant KV-cache memory. RWKV-CLIP [17] is a vision-language representation learner built around RWKV ideas and adapts RWKV-like architectures for high-resolution visual perception.

Alongside a growing body of work that rethinks the Transformer architecture to improve computational efficiency, a parallel line of research has emerged with a different emphasis: rather than optimizing hardware utilization or asymptotic complexity, these approaches seek to address limitations in abstraction, compositionality, and reasoning that arise from token-level autoregressive modeling. This shift reflects a broader recognition that architectural efficiency alone is insufficient, and that advances in representational structure and semantic modeling are equally critical for enabling more robust and generalizable intelligence. A particularly promising direction in this space is the development of Large Concept Models.

2.3. Large Concept Models

Large Concept Models (LCMs) [3], introduced by Meta, propose an alternative to token-based language modelling by shifting generation and reasoning into a semantic concept space rather than discrete token sequences. Instead of predicting the next word or subword, LCMs autoregressively predict the next sentence-level semantic embedding, where each embedding represents a full conceptual unit. This abstraction allows the model to operate at a higher level of meaning, potentially enabling more coherent reasoning over long contexts. LCMs rely on a pretrained, modality-agnostic embedding space which supports multilingual and multimodal representations. By decoupling reasoning from surface-level linguistic form, the model can generalize across languages and modalities without relying on language-specific tokenization. Compared to traditional large language models, this approach reduces sequence length and shifts the modeling focus from syntactic composition to semantic progression. While LCMs are primarily positioned as a complementary paradigm rather than a replacement for token-based models, they demonstrate how concept-level representations can support higher-level reasoning and abstraction in generative systems.

Cocomix [4], also an LCM by Meta, takes a more hybrid approach. It retains token-level next-token modelling but augments it with continuous concept prediction, giving the model an extra layer of abstraction reasoning without discarding the token modelling backbone. This hybrid approach achieves comparable performance to traditional next-token prediction models while utilizing 21.5% fewer training tokens, as well as consistently outperforms

knowledge distillation methods across various benchmarks like language modeling and downstream reasoning tasks.

In contrast to Mamba or RWKV, which primarily optimize computational efficiency, LCMs emphasize enhancing interpretability and abstraction capabilities (see Table 1). This makes LCM potentially well-suited for tasks requiring higher-level semantic understanding, such as vision-language integration. Despite this, there is a research gap in vision-language implementation of this concept-centric framework. This leaves an open opportunity to further explore how concept representations can enhance multimodal understanding, motivating our proposed integration of LCM into a prefix-based image captioning framework.

Table 1. LLM architectures comparison

Architecture	Key idea	Pros	Cons
Transformer	Full token-to-token self-attention	Strong state-of-the-art performance across tasks Very large ecosystem	$O(n^2)$ memory/compute Expensive for long contexts and high inference cost
Mamba	State-space model variant that achieves linear-time sequence processing and selective state propagation	Linear scaling with context, much lower memory/latency for very long sequences High throughput and strong long-context benchmarks	Smaller ecosystem and fewer pretrained checkpoints than Transformers Numerical stability tradeoffs for different SSM variants
RWKV	RNN-like recurrence with transformer-style parallel training Inference runs as linear RNN	Training parallelism like Transformers, RNN-like linear inference Lower runtime memory and cheaper inference	Less mature ecosystem than Transformers Sensitivity to hyperparameters, prompt format in practice
Cocomix	Augments next-token pretraining by predicting compressed continuous concepts to guide generation	More sample efficient Improves interpretability and steerability (concepts are inspectable, modifiable) Improves generalization	Underdeveloped ecosystem Additional pipeline complexity, extra training components, hyperparameters Applicability beyond tested scales/modalities still to be broadly validated

Chapter 3 METHODOLOGIES

3.1. ClipCap

Our models are built on ClipCap [5], a prefix-based image captioner that uses CLIP [18], a Contrastive Language-Image Pre-Training model developed by OpenAI, as the image encoders, followed by a Transformer block as mapping network, and finally a GPT-2 [19] text generator. This choice of architecture was made due to its relative simplicity and ease of modifying underlying components. This model works as followed (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. ClipCap architecture

Let I denote an input image and $T = [t_1, \dots, t_N]$ a sequence of text tokens, the image is encoded by CLIP and the mapping network MAP will map the image embedding into a sequence of GPT-compatible prefix embeddings of length l_p .

$$E_{img} = CLIP(I) \in R^{d_{CLIP}} \tag{1}$$

$$E_{prefix} = MAP(E_{img}) \in R^{l_p \times d_{GPT}}$$

Text embedding is created using GPT's embedding matrix over the token sequence and concatenated with the prefix embedding to create the final input:

$$E_{text} = GPT_E(T) \in R^{N \times d_{GPT}} \tag{2}$$

$$E_{full} = [E_{prefix}; E_{text}] \in R^{(l_p+N) \times d_{GPT}}$$

This input is fed to the GPT decoder to produce autoregressive token logits $z = GPT(E_{full})$.

Here, the standard objective is to learn a cross-entropy loss function:

$$\mathcal{L}_{lm} = - \sum_{n=1}^N \log p_{\theta} (t_n | t_{<n}, E_{prefix}) \quad (3)$$

Where $p_{\theta}(\cdot) = \text{softmax}(z)$ is the probability that the model assigns to the correct next token t_n given the previous tokens $t_{<n}$ and their embeddings.

3.2. Continuous Concept Mixing

Cocomix [4], built on GPT-2, works by augmenting the standard autoregressive language model with an additional “concept space” that captures higher-level semantic features in a continuous form (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Cocomix architecture

Given the token sequence $T = [t_1, \dots, t_N]$, a concept extractor $X = f_{con} \cdot h_{con}$ will predict next token probability $X_{con}(t_n | t_{<N})$ where we extract concept c from the hidden state h_{con} , and f_{con} will map that to the next token distribution. A sparse autoencoder (SAE) is trained on these hidden states to decompose them to multiple dimensions, capturing different semantically meaningful concept vectors.

$$c_n = TopK(E(h_n^{con})), \hat{h}_n^{con} = D(c_n) \quad (4)$$

Where E and D denote the encoder and decoder of the SAE respectively, and only the K largest activations are retained. Concept loss is calculated by minimizing cross-entropy function CE :

$$\mathcal{L}_{concept}(a_n) = \frac{1}{K_{attr}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{J}} CE(z_n, i) \quad (5)$$

Here, a_n is the attribution score [20], [21], \mathcal{J} is the set of indices corresponding to the top K_{attr} values of a_n , and linear layer M produces concept logits $z_n = M(h_n)$. Predicted logits are projected into continuous embeddings:

$$\hat{c}_n = W \text{TopK}(z_n) + b \quad (6)$$

Where W is the compression layer. The resulting continuous concept vector \hat{c}_n is treated as a separate unit, mixed with the hidden state as $(h_1, \hat{c}_1, \dots, h_n, \hat{c}_n)$ and fed into the remaining transformer blocks f for downstream prediction. The final objective would be to combine next-token prediction with concept supervision as followed.

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} [-\log f(t_{n+1} | h_{\leq n}, \hat{c}_{\leq n})] + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{concept}, \quad (7)$$

where λ is the tunable coefficient

In effect, by inserting those concepts as continuous vectors into the hidden state, the model is guided to build and attend to higher-level abstractions. This has three major benefits for reasoning tasks. First, it enables more sample-efficient learning of structure beyond token co-occurrence, which is especially helpful in long-range or compositional reasoning. Second, it improves generalization, the model can reuse learnt concept extractor in new contexts rather than relearn everything from scratch. Third, it yields greater interpretability and controllability, by surfacing the latent concepts, we can probe, steer, or intervene in the model’s reasoning process.

3.3. Our proposal

We propose incorporating the continuous concepts mixing method of Cocomix into ClipCap’s training process to capture more expressive semantic features (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. ClipCap with Cocomix integration

Given the tokens $T = [t_1, \dots, t_N]$, we apply the pretrained concept extractor X and retain only the K largest activations to get concept vector.

$$c = \text{TopK}(X(T)) \in R^{B \times N \times K} \quad (8)$$

At the same time, Cocomix outputs concept logits $z_{con} \in R^{B \times (l_p + N) \times d_{GPT}}$. As the extractor operates solely on tokens, concept supervision is applied only to text segment during training, causing a size mismatch between concept vector and logits. The simplest solution is to resize logits to remove prefix segment, then we compute concept loss via cross-entropy, which is combined with the language model's loss.

$$z_{textcon} = z_{con}[:, l_p:, :] \in R^{B \times N \times d_{GPT}}$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{concept}(a) = \frac{1}{K_{attr}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{J}} CE(z_{textcon}, i) \quad (9)$$

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{lm} + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{concept}$$

This solution allows Cocomix to be directly integrated into ClipCap with minimal architectural change. However, by excluding prefix segment of the logits from concept loss calculation, this deviates from the original training process of Cocomix which leverages concept extraction of the full input sequence, limiting potential concepts the model could have learned. To address this, we propose enabling concept extraction of prefix embedding.

3.4. Prefix Concept Extraction

The original ClipCap paper has demonstrated that, during the training process, the mapping network will be implicitly aligned with the language model’s embedding space. Meaning the prefix embedding already contains semantic features that can be directly converted into meaningful and relevant pseudo-tokens using Nearest-Neighbor lookup.

$$T_{prefix} = NN(E_{prefix}, GPT_E) = [t_1, \dots, t_{l_p}] \quad (10)$$

By concatenating pseudo-tokens T_{prefix} with text tokens T , we will have a full sequence that can be fed into concept extractor and computed for concept loss with the full logit $z_{con} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times (l_p + N) \times d_{GPT}}$.

$$T_{full} = [T_{prefix}; T] = [t_1, \dots, t_{l_p}, t_{l_p+1}, \dots, t_{l_p+N}]$$

$$c = TopK(X(T_{full})) \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times (l_p + N) \times K} \quad (11)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{concept}(a) = \frac{1}{K_{attr}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} C E(z_{con}, i)$$

In summary, the original approach restricts concept extraction to text tokens only, requiring the removal of the prefix segment from the logits to ensure dimensional consistency. This, however, causes the model to lose valuable concept information. By converting the prefix embeddings into pseudo-tokens, we enable the full input sequence, both prefix and text, to be processed by the concept extractor. Consequently, the concept loss can be computed over the full logits, allowing for capturing more comprehensive concepts from the input.

This modification not only makes use of prefix for concept extraction, but also turns concept loss into a regularization clause that bridges modality gap, enabling explicit alignment between prefix and text embedding.

Chapter 4

IMPLEMENTATION

4.1. Dataset Overview

For this study, we employ the Flickr30k dataset [22], a widely used benchmark in image captioning research. Flickr30k contains approximately 31,000 images, each depicting diverse everyday scenes involving people, animals, and objects. Every image is paired with five human-authored captions, providing rich linguistic variability and enabling evaluation across both lexical overlap and semantic fidelity.

The dataset was chosen for three key reasons:

1. **Benchmark status:** Flickr30k is a common reference point in multimodal learning, ensuring comparability with prior studies.
2. **Linguistic diversity:** Multiple captions per image provide a broader range of semantic expressions, which is essential for evaluating concept-based models.
3. **Accessibility:** The dataset is publicly available and widely adopted, facilitating reproducibility of our experiments.

4.2. Dataset Preparation

To ensure consistency with prior work, we adopt the standard dataset split of 1,000 images for testing and the remaining 30,000 for training. No additional preprocessing was applied beyond resizing and normalization required by the CLIP encoder. This minimal preparation ensures that the evaluation focuses on the effectiveness of the proposed LCM-based captioning framework rather than dataset-specific modifications.

4.3. Training and Evaluation Configuration

We explore two training configurations: (1) a joint setup in which both the mapping network and generator are trained simultaneously, and (2) a constrained setup in which the generator is frozen and only the mapping network is optimized. For visual encoding, we employ a frozen CLIP model as the image encoder. As for language generators, we experiment with GPT-2 and Cocomix. Both models have a comparable activated parameter size of

approximately 69 million and are pretrained on 650 million tokens from the OpenWebText corpus [19] to ensure a consistent and fair comparison. Moreover, for Cocomix, we will compare variants trained with and without prefix concept extraction (PCE).

For evaluation, we adopt a comprehensive set of standard metrics widely used in image captioning tasks to assess both lexical overlap and semantic alignment between generated and reference captions. Specifically, we use BLEU scores [23] to measure n-gram precision, METEOR [24] to capture semantic and morphological variations, ROUGE [25] to evaluate similarity based on longest common subsequences, and CIDEr [26] to assess consensus between candidate and human-written captions using TF-IDF weighting. Additionally, we include BERTScore [27], which leverages contextual embeddings from pretrained language models to quantify semantic similarity at the sentence level. Together, these metrics provide a balanced evaluation of both surface-level fluency and deeper semantic fidelity in the generated captions.

4.4. Stable Diffusion WebUI and Extension

To facilitate seamless interaction with our image captioning model, we developed an extension integrated into the Stable Diffusion WebUI environment. Stable Diffusion WebUI is a widely used open-source local interface that provides a browser-based platform to interact with Generative AI models for image creation and editing. Its modular extension system enables external models and utilities to be incorporated directly into the user workflow.

Figure 4. Extension interface

The developed extension includes a primary interface that allows users to upload images for caption generation (see Figure 4 and Figure 5). Within this interface, users can choose between two available models: Cocomix (PCE variant) and GPT-2, referred to as NTP (Next-Token Prediction). Upon selection, the extension automatically retrieves the corresponding pretrained model weights from Hugging Face, a popular online repository for open-source machine learning models and datasets. The model weights would then be stored in Hugging Face’s local cache directory for faster loading in future sessions. After generating, captions can be copied directly to the clipboard or downloaded as plain text files for external use. Additionally, the extension maintains an in-memory caption history, enabling users to revisit and reload previously processed images along with their associated captions.

The choice of Stable Diffusion WebUI as the primary integration platform not only facilitates straightforward implementation of our captioning models but also contributes to the process of image dataset creation. By generating unified, natural language descriptions of user-produced images, the extension supports the development of structured datasets that can be leveraged for further training, evaluation, or analysis of multimodal models.

Figure 5. Extension flow-chart

Chapter 5

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Results

From Table 2, it is evident that the Cocomix PCE variant consistently outperforms the base Cocomix model across both configurations. This improvement indicates that converting prefix embedding into pseudo-tokens accelerates alignment process, leading to the extraction of more meaningful concepts. However, when examining the GPT-2 versions, notable performance discrepancies emerge between the two configurations.

Table 2. Evaluation results

Model	BLEU 1	BLEU 2	BLEU 3	BLEU 4	METEOR	ROUGE	CIDEr	BERTScore
Frozen language model								
GPT-2	0.5245	0.3516	0.2285	0.1460	0.1961	0.4844	0.4384	0.8922
Cocomix	0.5847	0.4016	0.2647	0.1737	0.2033	0.4982	0.4660	0.8953
Cocomix + PCE	0.6221	0.4267	0.2822	0.1841	0.2052	0.5060	0.4587	0.8967
Finetuned language model								
GPT-2	0.7056	0.4897	0.3328	0.2255	0.2239	0.5196	0.5620	0.9044
Cocomix	0.6856	0.4713	0.3167	0.2126	0.2171	0.5107	0.5195	0.9031
Cocomix + PCE	0.6929	0.4791	0.3241	0.2200	0.2198	0.5148	0.5366	0.9037

From Figure 6, we can see that in the frozen language model setting, GPT-2 underperforms with a BLEU-1 score of 0.5245, compared to 0.5847 and 0.6221 achieved by Cocomix and PCE, respectively. In contrast, under the fine-tuned setting, the performance gap narrows, with GPT-2 slightly outperforming both variants, achieving a BLEU-1 score of 0.7056, compared to 0.6856 for Cocomix and 0.6929 for PCE.

Figure 6. Evaluation comparison of models on BLEU-1, METEOR and BERTScore

Inference efficiency measured on Google Colab’s T4 GPU is reported in Table 3. GPT-2 exhibits the fastest generation speed, with an average end-to-end latency of 0.336s, a throughput of 220.93 tokens/s and average token-per-caption of 16.823. Cocomix and Cocomix PCE show slightly greater latencies of 0.372s and 0.375s, with the speed of 193.59 tokens/s and 192.51 tokens/s, respectively. During inference, both Cocomix variants produce nearly identical average token counts, 14.874 tokens for Cocomix and 14.051 tokens for PCE.

Table 3. Performance evaluation on Google Colab T4 GPU (frozen language model configuration)

Model	Latency (s)	Throughput (tokens/s)	Average sentence tokens
GPT-2	0.336	220.93	16.823
Cocomix	0.372	193.59	14.874
Cocomix + PCE	0.375	192.51	14.051

5.2. Discussion

The experimental results highlight several important insights into the role of Large Concept Models (LCMs) and Prefix Concept Extraction (PCE) in image captioning. First, the consistent improvements of the Cocomix PCE variant over the base Cocomix model

demonstrate that converting prefix embeddings into pseudo-tokens enables the concept extractor to operate on the full input sequence, thereby capturing richer semantic abstractions and improving captions. This confirms the finding in the ClipCap paper [5] that prefix embeddings contain latent semantic information which, in our experiments, can be leveraged to accelerate cross-modal alignment.

Second, the comparative performance between GPT-2 and Cocomix variants underscores the importance of training configuration. In the frozen language model setting, GPT-2 struggles to capture semantic fidelity while Cocomix benefits from concept supervision, which regularizes the learning process and encourages attention to higher-level abstractions. This advantage diminishes under fine-tuning where GPT-2 regains competitiveness due to its larger embedding size of 624 compared to Cocomix’s 512. This was an architectural decision made to keep a comparable representational capacity since Cocomix includes an additional concept head. Nonetheless, the ability of Cocomix to maintain strong generalization under frozen conditions highlights the value of concept-based modeling in scenarios where language models cannot be extensively retrained.

Third, inference behavior reveals trade-offs between efficiency and expressiveness. GPT-2 achieves slightly faster generation speeds and higher throughput than the Cocomix variants. This difference reflects the additional computational overhead introduced by concept extraction. The training process is also significantly longer due to the complexity of concept loss supervision.

Beyond computational efficiency, several other limitations warrant consideration. The reliance on Flickr30k, while a standard benchmark, restricts evaluation to relatively small-scale and domain-specific data. Larger and more diverse datasets could provide stronger evidence of generalization. Moreover, the evaluation metrics employed: BLEU, METEOR, ROUGE, CIDEr, and BERTScore, capture lexical and semantic overlap but do not fully reflect human judgments of caption quality. Incorporating human evaluation would provide a more holistic assessment of fluency, relevance, and usefulness.

Finally, while the Stable Diffusion WebUI integration demonstrates practical deployment, the extension remains limited to caption generation. Broader multimodal tasks such as visual

question answering or narrative generation were not explored, leaving open questions about the scalability of concept-based modeling across domains.

Chapter 6

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

6.1. Conclusion

This thesis investigated the application of Large Concept Models (LCMs) to the task of image captioning, making one of the first systematic attempts to evaluate concept-based language modeling within a vision–language generation setting. The core contribution of this work lies in the integration of Continuous Concept Mixing (Cocomix) into a prefix-based image captioning framework and the proposal of Prefix Concept Extraction (PCE), a novel mechanism that enables explicit concept supervision over both visual prefixes and textual tokens. By converting prefix embeddings into pseudo-tokens, PCE allows concept extraction to operate over the full multimodal input sequence, strengthening cross-modal alignment at the semantic level.

Through extensive experiments on the Flickr30k dataset, this study demonstrates that LCM-based captioners consistently achieve stronger semantic fidelity and improved alignment compared to traditional Transformer-based approaches under frozen language model training. The results show that concept supervision serves as an effective regularization mechanism, allowing LCM variants to generalize better when language model fine-tuning is constrained. While GPT-2 remains competitive when fully fine-tuned, the proposed Cocomix and Cocomix + PCE models highlight the advantages of concept-level modeling in scenarios where retraining large language models is impractical or undesirable.

Beyond empirical evaluation, this thesis also contributes a practical implementation by integrating the proposed models into the Stable Diffusion WebUI. This deployment demonstrates the feasibility of applying LCM-based captioning systems in real-world workflows, supporting both image caption generation and dataset creation for downstream multimodal research.

Overall, this work contributes both methodologically and empirically by (1) extending LCMs to image captioning, (2) introducing Prefix Concept Extraction as a means of explicit multimodal concept alignment, and (3) validating the approach through quantitative

evaluation and real-world deployment. These findings suggest that concept-based modeling offers a viable and promising alternative to pure token likelihood optimization in multimodal learning. At the same time, limitations such as increased training cost, slower inference, reliance on relatively small-scale datasets, and the absence of human evaluation highlight important directions for further refinement.

6.2. Future Work

Building on these findings, several directions for future research are proposed:

1. **Scaling to larger datasets:** Extending evaluation to datasets such as Conceptual Captions [28] would provide stronger evidence of generalization and robustness.
2. **Human-centered evaluation:** Incorporating human judgments of fluency, relevance, and usefulness would complement automated metrics and yield a more comprehensive assessment of caption quality.
3. **Efficiency improvements:** Exploring architectural optimizations or lightweight concept extraction methods could reduce training time and inference latency, making concept-based models more practical for deployment.
4. **Broader multimodal tasks:** Extending the framework beyond captioning to tasks such as visual question answering, storytelling, or multimodal reasoning would test the versatility of concept-based modeling.

By pursuing these directions, future work can further advance the role of LCMs in multimodal learning, ensuring that concept-based approaches not only improve semantic fidelity but also scale effectively, generalize broadly, and serve real-world applications responsibly.

References

- [1] A. Vaswani *et al.*, “Attention is All you Need,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, I. Guyon, U. V. Luxburg, S. Bengio, H. Wallach, R. Fergus, S. Vishwanathan, and R. Garnett, Eds., Curran Associates, Inc., 2017. [Online]. Available: https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2017/file/3f5ee243547dee91fbd053c1c4a845aa-Paper.pdf
- [2] J. Wei *et al.*, “Chain-of-Thought Prompting Elicits Reasoning in Large Language Models,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, S. Koyejo, S. Mohamed, A. Agarwal, D. Belgrave, K. Cho, and A. Oh, Eds., Curran Associates, Inc., 2022, pp. 24824–24837. [Online]. Available: https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2022/file/9d5609613524ecf4f15af0f7b31abca4-Paper-Conference.pdf
- [3] L. C. M. team *et al.*, “Large Concept Models: Language Modeling in a Sentence Representation Space.” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.08821>
- [4] J. Tack *et al.*, “LLM Pretraining with Continuous Concepts.” 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.08524>
- [5] R. Mokady, A. Hertz, and A. H. Bermano, “ClipCap: CLIP Prefix for Image Captioning.” 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2111.09734>
- [6] J. Li, D. Li, S. Savarese, and S. Hoi, “BLIP-2: Bootstrapping Language-Image Pre-training with Frozen Image Encoders and Large Language Models,” in *Proceedings of the 40th International Conference on Machine Learning*, A. Krause, E. Brunskill, K. Cho, B. Engelhardt, S. Sabato, and J. Scarlett, Eds., in *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 202. PMLR, July 2023, pp. 19730–19742. [Online]. Available: <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v202/li23q.html>
- [7] T. M. Huynh, D. L. Nguyen, T. T. Nguyen, T.-D. T. Vu, H. Dang-Ngoc, and D. N. M. Dang, “CLIP-Prefix for Image Captioning and an Experiment on Blind Image Guessing,” in *Industrial Networks and Intelligent Systems*, N.-S. Vo, D.-B. Ha, and H. Jung, Eds., Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, pp. 189–203.
- [8] X. Zhang *et al.*, “Unified Multimodal Understanding and Generation Models: Advances, Challenges, and Opportunities.” 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.02567>
- [9] J. Lu *et al.*, “Unified-IO 2: Scaling Autoregressive Multimodal Models with Vision Language Audio and Action,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, June 2024, pp. 26439–26455.
- [10] J. Wu *et al.*, “VisionLLM v2: An End-to-End Generalist Multimodal Large Language Model for Hundreds of Vision-Language Tasks,” in *Advances in Neural Information*

- Processing Systems*, A. Globerson, L. Mackey, D. Belgrave, A. Fan, U. Paquet, J. Tomczak, and C. Zhang, Eds., Curran Associates, Inc., 2024, pp. 69925–69975. [Online]. Available: https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2024/file/81a60d18e010b27b36cd465c6604b915-Paper-Conference.pdf
- [11] J.-B. Alayrac *et al.*, “Flamingo: a Visual Language Model for Few-Shot Learning.” 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2204.14198>
- [12] Z. Wu *et al.*, “DeepSeek-VL2: Mixture-of-Experts Vision-Language Models for Advanced Multimodal Understanding.” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.10302>
- [13] Y. Li *et al.*, “Uni-MoE: Scaling Unified Multimodal LLMs With Mixture of Experts,” *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.*, vol. 47, no. 5, pp. 3424–3439, 2025, doi: 10.1109/TPAMI.2025.3532688.
- [14] A. Gu and T. Dao, “Mamba: Linear-Time Sequence Modeling with Selective State Spaces.” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.00752>
- [15] A. Hatamizadeh and J. Kautz, “MambaVision: A Hybrid Mamba-Transformer Vision Backbone,” in *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, June 2025.
- [16] B. Peng *et al.*, “RWKV: Reinventing RNNs for the Transformer Era,” in *Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:258832459>
- [17] T. Gu *et al.*, “RWKV-CLIP: A Robust Vision-Language Representation Learner,” in *Proceedings of the 2024 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, Y. Al-Onaizan, M. Bansal, and Y.-N. Chen, Eds., Miami, Florida, USA: Association for Computational Linguistics, Nov. 2024, pp. 4799–4812. doi: 10.18653/v1/2024.emnlp-main.276.
- [18] A. Radford *et al.*, “Learning Transferable Visual Models From Natural Language Supervision.” 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.00020>
- [19] A. Radford, J. Wu, R. Child, D. Luan, D. Amodei, and I. Sutskever, “Language Models are Unsupervised Multitask Learners,” 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:160025533>
- [20] D. Baehrens, T. Fiddike, S. Harmeling, M. Kawanabe, K. Hansen, and K.-R. Müller, “How to Explain Individual Classification Decisions,” *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, vol. 11, Dec. 2009.
- [21] M. Sundararajan, A. Taly, and Q. Yan, “Axiomatic attribution for deep networks,” in *Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Machine Learning - Volume 70*, in ICML’17. Sydney, NSW, Australia: JMLR.org, 2017, pp. 3319–3328.

- [22] P. Young, A. Lai, M. Hodosh, and J. Hockenmaier, “From image descriptions to visual denotations: New similarity metrics for semantic inference over event descriptions,” *TACL*, vol. 2, pp. 67–78, Dec. 2014, doi: 10.1162/tacl_a_00166.
- [23] K. Papineni, S. Roukos, T. Ward, and W.-J. Zhu, “Bleu: a Method for Automatic Evaluation of Machine Translation,” in *Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 2002. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:11080756>
- [24] A. Lavie and A. Agarwal, “METEOR: An Automatic Metric for MT Evaluation with High Levels of Correlation with Human Judgments,” in *WMT@ACL*, 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:16289845>
- [25] C.-Y. Lin, “ROUGE: A Package for Automatic Evaluation of Summaries,” in *Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 2004. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:964287>
- [26] R. Vedantam, C. L. Zitnick, and D. Parikh, “CIDEr: Consensus-based image description evaluation,” *2015 IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. CVPR*, pp. 4566–4575, 2014.
- [27] T. Zhang, V. Kishore, F. Wu, K. Q. Weinberger, and Y. Artzi, “BERTScore: Evaluating Text Generation with BERT,” *ArXiv*, vol. abs/1904.09675, 2019, [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:127986044>
- [28] P. Sharma, N. Ding, S. Goodman, and R. Soricut, “Conceptual Captions: A Cleaned, Hypernymed, Image Alt-text Dataset For Automatic Image Captioning,” in *Proceedings of the 56th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)*, I. Gurevych and Y. Miyao, Eds., Melbourne, Australia: Association for Computational Linguistics, July 2018, pp. 2556–2565. doi: 10.18653/v1/P18-1238.